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On the Planned Apprenticeship Guarantee for Germany: An Attempt to Reduce the Risk of Social Exclusion During the Transition from School to VET?

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Abstract

At the end of 2022, the German government published a draft for an apprenticeship guarantee. One measure proposed in the draft is to fund apprenticeships for those young people who do not find an apprenticeship despite actively searching. It is assumed that around 7,000 young people would start such extra-company training each year. This number seems rather low compared to the more than 200,000 young people who start preparatory courses every year. In the 18-34 age group, the risk of unemployment is five times higher if a person has not obtained a vocational or higher education qualification – this goes along with other forms of social exclusion. The paper raises the question of whether such an apprenticeship guarantee, due to its small scale, could only bring about minor changes for the disadvantaged, or whether it could represent a paradigm shift on a conceptual and political level, as it aims to integrate disadvantaged young people directly into the regular system instead of separating them from the rest.

Keywords

access to education and training, education and training reform, Germany, policy implications, social inclusion

1 Introduction

In 2021, the German government declared its intention to introduce an apprenticeship guarantee (SPD et al., 2021, p. 66). One year later, at the end of 2022, the Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs presented a draft bill and a shorter concept paper for the apprenticeship guarantee (Bundesministerium für Arbeit und Soziales [BMAS], 2022a, 2022b). This article analyses this political reform initiative, which addresses a long-known shortcoming of the German VET system: The lack of a fully qualified VET option for those school leavers who cannot find an apprenticeship. Since the adoption of the Vocational Training Act in 1969, there have been several attempts to introduce some form of apprenticeship guarantee in (West) Germany – all of which have so far failed (Busemeyer, 2009). Using the approach of critical policy analysis, this paper discusses the ministerial draft bill in context of the social and political situation in Germany. Research questions are:

- What are the elements of the draft apprenticeship guarantee and what are the reasons to introduce such a proposal?
- What social problems and structural aspects of the German VET system does the draft apprenticeship guarantee address?
- What is the political constellation behind this reform initiative and what are the possible outcomes of such an apprenticeship guarantee?

2 Reform proposal: An apprenticeship guarantee for Germany

The ministerial bill calls for "strengthening support for initial and continuing vocational training and the introduction of a training period"¹. The bill includes a larger legislative package for the reform of the German Social Code (Sozialgesetzbuch, SGB). It does not deal exclusively with the apprenticeship guarantee, but the following discussion will only focus on this aspect, as there is no internal connection with the other parts of the bill. Notably, the draft bill is designed in the context of German labour market regulation rather than as an education reform, since educational policy is mainly the responsibility of the 16 German federal states (*Länder*).

The aim of the apprenticeship guarantee is to give all young people without a vocational qualification access to a fully qualifying, preferably in-company vocational training.² To this end, the bill proposes four measures: (1) strengthening vocational orientation, (2) increasing regional mobility, (3) preparing for and supporting in-company vocational training and (4) offering extra-company vocational training as an "ultima ratio" (BMAS, 2022b, pp. 3–7). These measures relate to different aspects of finding an apprenticeship and are regulated in different paragraphs of the SGB.

As a first step – strengthening vocational orientation – existing careers guidance should be improved to help young people find a training place in their region. To this end, the Ministry also calls on the *Länder* to set up a data exchange that enables the Federal Employment Agency to contact school leavers (BMAS, 2022b, pp. 3–4). As a new instrument (new §48a SGB III), the Ministry proposes that the Federal Employment Agency should finance internships between one and six weeks for young people without an apprenticeship position (BMAS, 2022a, p. 6).

As a second step, young people shall be supported in finding an apprenticeship in another region. In addition to the announcement of further efforts to expand residential facilities (BMAS, 2022a, pp. 4–5), an individual allowance (new §73a SGB III) is planned for trainees who move to another region (BMAS, 2022a, pp. 8–9).

The third step – preparation and support for in-company training – refers to improving existing opportunities for preparatory courses and individual assistance. The only change announced here is a reduction in the minimum duration of long-term work internships for young people without an apprenticeship from six to four months (BMAS, 2022b, pp. 5–6).

Only as a last step – as an "ultima ratio" after all the above measures have been applied – is the Federal Employment Agency to offer fully qualifying extra-company vocational training opportunities. There is already a legal possibility for young people to conclude an apprenticeship contract with a private training provider that is financed by the Federal Employment Agency, but this option is restricted to socially disadvantaged and learning-disabled persons (§76 SGB III). The draft bill proposes to expand the group of eligible participants to include all young people who have not found an apprenticeship despite actively searching for one (BMAS, 2022a, p. 14).

¹ German title: „Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Stärkung der Aus- und Weiterbildungsförderung und Einführung einer Bildungszeit“.

² German original: „Um allen jungen Menschen, die nicht über einen Berufsabschluss verfügen, den Zugang zu einer vollqualifizierenden, möglichst betrieblichen Berufsausbildung zu eröffnen, wird eine Ausbildungsgarantie eingeführt.“ BMAS (2022a, p. 3).

This brief summary of the proposed apprenticeship guarantee shows that only this last step aims to create additional apprenticeship offers, while the other elements are designed to make the use of this measure – the ultima ratio – dispensable. The Ministry assumes that around 7,000 young people would start such extra-company training each year (BMAS, 2022a, p. 37). Wherever possible, extra-company vocational training should take place in cooperation with regular companies. Transition into regular in-company vocational training should be possible and intended. The apprentice shall be able to continue the training with accreditation of the time previously completed. Continued socio-pedagogical assistance by the previous training provider should be possible after the transfer (BMAS, 2022a, pp. 34–35).

The need for the entire reform proposal is justified above all by the structural change in the economy and the shortage of skilled workers. The competitiveness and innovative capacity of the German economy is the higher goal. For this, a sufficient number of skilled workers are needed and the workforce must be trained accordingly (BMAS, 2022a, 2-4, 29-32). In this context, the apprenticeship guarantee is an instrument to prevent young people from entering the labour market without vocational qualification; making their employability the main goal. On the other hand, this employability is framed as a way to offer all young people the chance of secure future prospects and thus the key to social inclusion (BMAS, 2022a, p. 36).

The necessity for an apprenticeship guarantee is then specifically justified by the fact that despite an existing shortage of skilled workers, not all young people find an apprenticeship. The reason for this is essentially seen in matching problems. Hence, priority should be given to better vocational guidance and counselling as well as to providing more internships and facilitating regional mobility to make full use of companies' existing apprenticeship offers. For young people who cannot find a regular apprenticeship, additional apprenticeship opportunities should be created in line with the regional economic structure and needs (BMAS, 2022a, p. 34). An additional reason mentioned is the implementation of the European Youth Guarantee (BMAS, 2022a, p. 32), which was first adopted in 2013 and last updated in 2020 (European Council, 2020).

4 Context: School-to-VET transition and the risk of social exclusion

The German educational system is based on compulsory education for all children in primary and lower secondary education until the age of 15 to 16 years. In this respect, education systems around the world are quite similar (OECD, 2022, p. 429). In contrast, VET systems differ a lot. In Europe, three types of VET systems exist: A liberal market model (e.g. in England), a state focussed education-driven model (e.g. in France) and a dual system (e.g. in Germany) (Greinert, 2004).

The strong advantage of dual systems is their proximity to the labour market. Because of the high transition rate from in-company apprenticeship to work, dual VET systems are associated with low youth unemployment. The European Union is therefore promoting dual VET as a measure against high youth unemployment (European Council, 2013). Even though the number of new apprentices decreased sharply in Germany due to the COVID-19 pandemic, the employment opportunities of young people in the dual VET track remain positive (Mouillour, 2022).

VET in Germany offers a non-academic route to secure and decent employment. Without a VET qualification, the prospects are rather poor. Unskilled young people – around 15 % in the 18-34 age group – are five times more likely to be unemployed (15.7 % vs. 3.2 %) (Bundesinstitut für Berufsbildung [BIBB], 2022, p. 255). This nexus is well known from other countries: “It has become a widely held assumption that those young people who are outside all education, training or employment between the ages of sixteen and eighteen are condemned to an economically and socially marginalised future.” (Rinne & Järvinen, 2010, p. 521)

Therefore, the vulnerability of the German VET system lies especially in the access to apprenticeships. Even during the economic boom of the last decade, when skilled labour was scarce, many low-performing school leavers failed to enter apprenticeships. And of those who enter preparatory programmes, more than a third do not start an apprenticeship in the four years after leaving school. Those most at risk of not entering the VET system are those who leave lower secondary school without a diploma or with a lower-level diploma (*Hauptschulabschluss*). Four years after leaving school, 27% of girls and 20% of boys in this group have neither successfully completed an apprenticeship nor are they currently in one (Michaelis et al., 2022, pp. 83–87). Other risk factors for the transition from school to VET include parents with a low socio-economic status and low educational attainment, as well as immigrant background (Michaelis et al., 2022, p. 42; see also Autorinnengruppe Bildungsberichterstattung, 2022, Chapter E). The social transmission of disadvantages from parents to their children through the education system is evident in this context (Eckelt & Burkard, 2022, p. 26).

Figure 1

Beginners in educational sectors & cohort at the end of lower secondary (by year)

Sources: destatis: Integrierte Ausbildungsberichterstattung; Fachserie 11 Reihe 1 (different years)

In Germany the number of young people leaving school has declined in the last years. Currently, about 800,000 pupils are in the 9th grade, the last year of obligatory lower secondary education. After finishing their lower secondary education, young people have different possibilities for how and when to enter educational courses. During the last decade before the COVID-19 pandemic, around 700,000 persons began a VET course each year, almost 500,000 of them in the dual VET system. Around $\frac{1}{3}$ of the German VET systems consists of so-called school-based vocational courses outside the dual VET system. VET in health, education and social professions is not regulated by the national Vocational Training Act mentioned above, but by various laws of the *Länder* and the federal state. Another 500,000 persons enrol in universities each year, which is the alternative way to a professional qualification next to the VET system.

Even though the numbers of those entering preparatory courses (*Übergangssektor*) are declining in the last 15 years, still more than 200,000 young people enter those programs each year. These persons need to enter a VET programme or – less likely – a university programme

to acquire a professional qualification. They can therefore be counted as an indicator of potential additional demand for apprenticeships.³

During the last decades, German VET policymakers created various educational programmes for those with difficulties to access the VET system. These programmes, however, were not able to solve the problem of a significant share of school leavers to find an apprenticeship. Due to the formal requirements for access, dual training is usually the most likely option for this group as it is the only programme that does not require proof of a specific school-leaving qualification. In fact, the access to apprenticeships in the dual VET system is organized like a job market: companies offer training places and have a free hand in the selection of apprentices. Their contracts usually last three years. During this time, the apprentice receives a monthly payment by the company. Besides working in the company, apprentices also visit vocational schools (see for an overview, Cedefop, 2020).

Depending on the relation of supply and demand on this market, either the companies looking for new apprentices or the school leavers looking for an apprenticeship are in a better position (BIBB, 2022, pp. 15–25). Such a market model explains very well, why a significant number of school leavers are not able to find an apprenticeship when the number of school leavers is rising or when there is an economic crisis. But the fact that there are still more than 200,000 young people entering preparatory courses after years of economic growth shows the need for more complex models. A first theoretical auxiliary construction is the assumption that market participants are unwilling to accept offers that do not meet their minimum expectations. In this way, apprenticeships on the one hand and training applicants on the other hand can remain without a match, even though there would still be a suitable offer in purely mathematical terms (Kohlrausch, 2012).

5 Discussion: Minor changes or paradigm shift?

In view of the dimensions of the social problem described above, the Ministry's proposal for an apprenticeship guarantee is surprising in purely quantitative terms: 7,000 additional extra-company apprenticeships could only create an alternative offer for a fraction of those who are entering preparatory courses each year. Assuming that this instrument worked with a 100% success rate and that 7,000 more people successfully completed an apprenticeship each year, this would reduce the 15% of young people without a vocational qualification by only one percentage point.⁴

The proposal focuses only on the dual VET system and aims to give more power to the Federal Employment Agency. The reasons for this lie mainly in legislative competencies of the Federal Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs that simply has no legal competencies in the other fields of the (vocational) education system. Additional apprenticeships outside the dual system are not taken into account, which is problematic from a gender perspective as women enter VET in health, education and social professions disproportionately.

³ Each year, the total number of beginners in the various sectors is significantly higher than the number of pupils of one cohort. This is mainly due to the fact that people use more than one of those educational opportunities in their educational biography. In addition, these statistics in Germany are not based on individual data. Therefore, there can be multiple counts within a year. The positive immigration balance in Germany, almost exclusively into higher education, also comes into play here. The numbers relating to dual VET deviate slightly from the most frequently cited numbers. They come from a different set of statistics with a different cut-off date than the figures published by BIBB. However, these numbers are also used by BIBB for the sector comparison. See: BIBB (2022, p. 79).

⁴ Austria introduced an apprenticeship guarantee in the late 1990s. The German proposal is clearly inspired by this Austrian model. In 2020, around 7 % of all Austrian apprentices had an apprenticeship contract with a private training provider. See: Wieland (2020).

On the political level, the reform initiative might challenge the balance of power between trade and industry umbrella associations, trade union confederations and the state, which are the main actors of the German tripartite governance in the VET policy field. Not surprisingly, the trade and industry umbrella associations refuse the proposal as such. They deny that there are too few apprenticeship offers in Germany. In contrast, they put the problems of the companies finding apprentices into the spotlight (Redaktionsnetzwerk Deutschland, 2022). From this perspective, young people are not in VET, either due to their missing initiative or necessary qualifications. On the other hand, the trade unions demand an apprenticeship guarantee, but refer mainly to it as an apprenticeship levy to be paid by companies (DGB-Bundesvorstand, 2022). These actors are thus continuing a political dispute that goes back to the 1970s, when such a levy was introduced and a few years later abolished again due to legal formalities (Steib & Ketschau, 2022).

Given that the constellation between the social partners has not changed, the question arises as to why the Ministry has put this issue back on the agenda. Two reasons show up here: Firstly, Germany's largest private think tank, the Bertelsmann Foundation, has launched a political campaign in favour of the apprenticeship guarantee, which has been joined by other political actors such as the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung.⁵ Secondly, Minister Hubertus Heil (SPD) has been pursuing a correction of earlier liberalisations of the labour market and also with regard to dual VET for several years. The introduction of a minimum training allowance in 2020 can in this regard be seen as a blueprint for the current situation (BMAS, 2020). As an overarching research question for the next years, it can be asked whether the German state has abandoned its traditional restraint in the field of VET policy and to what extent.

From an educational and moral philosophical perspective, an education guarantee addresses a problem of justice. In modern Western societies inequality is considered morally acceptable only if it is not the result of chance but of individual choice and merit (Rawls, 1971). In this context, education systems have a key role to play. “Hence, to allow significant inequalities of schooling tends to exclude children from socially and economically disadvantaged families from access to elite positions. Therefore, inequalities of schooling threaten the dignity of the disadvantaged.” (Giesinger, 2011, p. 53) Obviously, in the case of an apprenticeship guarantee, the issue is not access to elite positions, but whether young people have a realistic chance at all of finding a decent job with a stable income as a skilled worker, or whether they are at high risk of poverty and dependence on state welfare.

Lacking education and training opportunities, youth unemployment and early school leaving are challenges that – next to others – constitute an important European policy field (Siurala, 2007). European youth policy aims to prevent social exclusion of disadvantaged groups in all member states. Also, in the rich and ‘educationally most successful’ countries like Finland, social exclusion in the transition from school to work is a problem (Rinne & Järvinen, 2010). Social exclusion as a form of social injustice is always a relative concept that implies comparison. There is no such thing as an absolute standard, neither with regard to the social categories nor to the place of comparison (Sen, 2009). There are many aspects and forms of social exclusion, which affect different groups. A paradoxical effect of tackling social inequality is that it often leads to an increased awareness of new inequalities and injustices (El-Mafaalani, 2021, p. 55). Thus, such social problems cannot be completely eradicated. Rather, there is a dialectic of inclusion and exclusion that creates a constant tension in society. In the field of VET, the intent to tackle social exclusion has led to political reforms that create supplementary educational offers in the VET system. This dynamic is not only evident in

⁵ See the campaign website <https://ausbildungsgarantie.de> and the concept for an apprenticeship guarantee published by Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung: Euler and Seeber (2023).

Germany, but also in other countries. The result has been the creation of specialised courses to prevent the social exclusion of specific groups, such as school drop-outs or refugees (Jørgensen et al., 2021; Marhuenda et al., 2015).

On this conceptual level, the question that arises is whether the proposal for the apprenticeship guarantee indicates a paradigm shift in the German context, as it aims to integrate disadvantaged young people directly into the regular system instead of separating them into preparatory training courses. In this respect, this approach is reminiscent of the inclusion paradigm known from the debate on people with disabilities. To tackle their social exclusion in the educational system, the idea of inclusive education became popular in the international educational policy debate in the 1990s. Inclusion is not strictly defined, but it is “an idea, a word, a term, or a pedagogical concept that ‘travelled far’, was used in different ways, and thereby gained a whole variety of meanings” (Kiuppis, 2016). In that sense, the proposal may be interpreted as a cautious attempt at a paradigmatic reorientation simply by offering a conceptual alternative to existing problems. The small number of apprenticeship seekers affected by the guarantee could then be addressed at a later phase by scaling the instrument.

At this moment, one can only speculate about the empirical effects of the apprenticeship guarantee. First of all, it remains to be seen whether and in what form the reform will be carried out. Should the apprenticeship guarantee really come, its introduction will be a worthwhile object of research for VET research in the coming years. In the end, the utility of such an instrument has to prove itself in practice by enabling more young people to start and successfully complete an apprenticeship. Research to accompany the process is absolutely necessary to assess whether and how this is being achieved.

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